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Mechanical evaluation of cementitious composites reinforced with sugarcane bagasse fibres

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Abstract. This paper describes the physical and compressive properties of cementitious composites reinforced with sugarcane bagasse fibres. Saturated organic acids (stearic acid and castor oil) reagents are used as fibre modifiers. A 3² factorial Design of Experiment (DoE) is used to statistically evaluate the fibre amount and treatment factors. Treated fibre composites achieve higher mechanical properties with increase by up to 22.25% and lower physical properties, reduce by up to 20.46% in relation to the reference mortar (no fibres).

1. Introduction

There is a growing interest in obtaining composites containing natural fibres in civil construction, mainly due to their wide availability and eco-friendly [1, 2]. Various fibres help with concrete limitations, as they reduce crack growth [3-5]. Some works shows synthetic fibres to reinforce concrete structures however, its production has a high cost and is not sustainability viable [6-8]. Therefore, the replacement of synthetic fibres with natural fibres becomes a good alternative in projects focused on renewable characteristics [9, 10].

Fibre reinforced composites depend on the properties of their phases, that includes composition, volume fraction, interface and their interactions. However, natural fibres possess are constituted of hemicellulose and cellulose with many hydroxyl groups that make them hydrophilic [11]. Natural fibres in cementitious composites can absorb additional water from the system, affecting cement hydration and their properties [12, 13]. Therefore, the chemical modification of natural fibres has been the most explored way in the literature to overcome these difficulties. The use of fatty acids, that are natural products obtained from animal and vegetable fats, as surface

modifiers for cellulose, has been widely discussed in the literature as an efficient method to introduce hydrophobic character into the fibre [14, 15]. The stearic acid is one of the most cited fibre modifiers in the literature.

This work uses stearic acid and castor oil reagents as modifiers of sugarcane bagasse (scb) fibres. The fibres are incorporated into cementitious composites for secondary structural applications in civil construction. A robust statistical design identifies the effects of individual factors and their interactions on the physical and mechanical properties with high sensitivity and optimises the material's composition.

2. Methodology

2.1. Fibre treatment

Firstly, the scb fibres are sieved over the particle size range of 16 to 30 US-Tyler, then washed with distilled water and oven-dried at 100°C for approximately 24 h. The fibres are placed in a 10% (m/v) NaOH solution for a pre-treatment, in the proportion of 1 g to 5 mL, for 90 min, then washed with distilled water until pH = 7. Finally, the fibres are taken to the oven-dry for 24 h at 100°C. After this pre-treatment, the fibres are immersed in ethanolic solutions of stearic acid and castor oil, in concentrations of 20% (m/v), in the proportion of 1 g of fibres to 20 mL of solution. The fibres are left on a shaker table for 24 h. After this time, they are placed in an oven at 100°C for 24 h for drying. Untreated fibres are called scb, and fibres treated with stearic acid and castor oil are called scbsa and scbco, respectively.

2.2. Sample preparation and characterisation

Samples for the mechanical test are prepared according to ASTM C192 [16] protocols. Cementitious composites are a mortar-based mixture composed of one part of cement, three parts of standardised sand (20 wt% of fine, 50 wt% of medium and 30 wt% of coarse aggregates) and a water/cement ratio of 0.55. The mortar-based mixture is combined with the bagasse fibres, poured into polyvinyl chloride (PVC) cylindrical moulds set on a glass base. The moulds are 50 mm in diameter by 100 mm in height, following the 1:2 ratio recommended for the compression test. A vibrating table is used for 5 minutes to homogenise the material inside the mould. Then, the composites are wrapped with plastic film to prevent water loss to the environment. The composites are demoulded after 7 days and left at room temperature (~22°C).

Compressive samples are tested after 28 days of curing. Cementitious composites are tested in compression at 1 mm/min according to ASTM C348-14 [17]. The test is performed on a Shimadzu Autograph AG-X Plus machine equipped with a 100 kN cell load. Physical properties such as apparent porosity and apparent density are determined following BS 10545-3 [18].

2.3. Statistical experimental design

Table 1 shows a 3² full factorial design to the factors analysed, the type of fibre (scb, scbsa and scbco) and the amount of fibre (2, 5 and 10 wt%), with three levels each. A reference condition (non-reinforced composite) is also prepared for comparison.

The Design of Experiment (DoE) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) techniques are performed using Minitab[™] v19 [19] software to verify the significance of each factor on the responses, considering a 95% confidence interval. Interaction plots are used to interpret and analyse the results.

Table 1. Full Factorial Design (3²).

Experimental conditions	Fibre type	Fibre amount/wt%
1	scb	2
2	scb	5
3	scb	10
4	scbsa	2
5	scbsa	5
6	scbsa	10
7	scbco	2
8	scbco	5
9	scbco	10

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Apparent density

Figure 1 shows the interaction effect plot for the mean apparent density. Density fitted means range from 2278.71 to 2451.30 kg/m³. The incorporation of treated fibres reduces the density of the composites (scbsa and scbco) compared to the untreated fibre composites (scb) and the reference condition. Increasing the amount of lightweight bagasse fibres to cementitious composites reduces their density. As the amount of fibre increases, the reduction in density is more effective for all fibre types, especially when the factor level changes from 5 wt% to 10 wt%.

Fig. 1. Interaction effect plots for the fitted means of apparent density.

4.2. Apparent porosity

The interaction effect plots for mean apparent porosity is shown in Fig. 2. The increase in the amount of fibres would increase the composites porosity, attributed mainly to the increase in the interfacial zones between the fibres and the matrix phase. In contrast, treated fibres (scbsa and scbco) reduce porosity compared to untreated fibres (scb). This behaviour demonstrates that the fibres change from hydrophilic (scb) to hydrophobic (scbsa and scbco) characteristic after chemical treatment. The apparent porosity data range from 15.91 to 30.42 %.

Fig. 2. Interaction effect plots for the fitted means of apparent porosity.

4.3. Compressive strength

Fig. 3 exhibits the interaction effect plot for the mean compressive strength. Compared to the reference condition (see grey dashed line), fibre incorporation is only beneficial for strength when treated with stearic acid (scbsa). It is worth mentioning that chemical treatment plays a role in the compressive strength of cementitious composites. The fitted means range from 2.50 to 49.30 MPa. It is noted that fibre levels of 2 wt% and 5 wt% lead to similar enhanced effects on strength. The highest strength (49.30 MPa) presented by the interaction plot is 18.54% higher than the reference mortar without fibre reinforcement (41.59 MPa). This result indicates that even in small amounts of bagasse fibres treated with a particular reagent, it is possible to improve the mechanical performance of mortar composites.

Fig. 3. Interaction effect plots for the fitted means of compressive strength.

5. Conclusions

To reinforce cementitious composites, the sugarcane bagasse fibres were treated with stearic acid and castor oil and was verified the fibre amount 2, 5 and 10 wt%. Fibre treatment significantly affects most physical and mechanical properties. Treated fibre composites reduce apparent density and porosity to the untreated fibre samples. In contrast, increased strength are achieved by treated fibre composites compared to untreated fibre mortar. The increase in fibre amount leads to a reduction in apparent density and strength as well as an increase in porosity. Finally, the findings reveal that sugarcane bagasse fibres, treated with a specific reagent, can modify and improve mortars' physical and mechanical properties, promoting a sustainable route and recycling of agro-industrial wastes.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Ana Cláudia dos Santos: Methodology, Conceptualisation, Investigation, Data Curation, Validation, Visualisation, Writing - Original Draft. **Rodrigo José da Silva:** Software, Formal analysis, Visualisation, Writing - Original Draft. **Honória de Fátima Gorgulho:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualisation, Writing - Original Draft. **Túlio Hallak Panzera:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualisation, Writing - Review & Editing.

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